

Comparative Study on MBA Programmes in Private & Public Universities - A case study of MBA programme plan of Srinivas University

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Abstract

The MBA (Master of Business Administration) degree is perhaps the world's best known and most widely recognized post graduate degree. It is a professional degree - in that it prepares or further prepares individuals for responsible positions in business - usually managerial positions. Despite its venerable age (the first MBA degrees were awarded in the early twentieth century), MBA programmes remain both popular and relevant. MBA programs are run throughout the world, as they are seen to be relevant for the preparation of people for work in management irrespective of the industry, business sector, the nature of the economy, etc. Although critics of the programmes have been numerous, large companies and increasingly small ones as well continue to see real value in the MBA as the first stage in a professional career in management. In this paper, the public and private universities are compared based on their ability to provide quality and innovative post graduate business management education in terms of quality, latest innovative curriculum, specialisations, programme duration, foreign exposure, industry orientation, networking, placement service, total credits for the programme, course fee structure, and examination system. Comparison is done by considering some of public and private universities and their ability to add values to the programme in the frame of stakeholder's reference. Finally, the advantages benefits, constraints and disadvantages of public and private universities are identified and are listed under organisational, students, faculty, parents and societal issues using focus group method.

Keywords : Innovations in business education; MBA programme; Private university; Public university.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indian higher education is not only large in scope but complex in its working and evolution. One indicator is existence of four different types of universities depending on who funds them and regulates them. For example, Deemed to be Universities come under the purview of UGC and are mostly funded by private resources. They were also in controversy for corruption and qualitative deficiencies for profiteering. This also tainted the name of some of the better quality private Deemed to be Universities. Given the regulatory and media attention to the deficiencies with Deemed to be Universities, Private Universities gained attraction. This is evident from their growth from 100 to 140 in less than a year as compared to no growth of Deemed to be Universities in the same period. The private universities are working hard to attract students away from central and state universities by offering differentiated courses incorporating features like triple mains, super-specializations, dual degrees, integrated programs, CBCS, and industry affiliated courses. It is tougher for self-financing colleges to rapidly implement such measures as they can move only at the speed of the affiliating state universities that often take ages to implement an innovation [1].

The best example is the Choice Based Credit System (CBCS), which the UGC has been coaxing all public universities to implement. Till now, there has been only very few takers for this global standard, whereas many leading private universities have already implemented it without any prompting, as a progressive measure. Private Universities have also turned aggressive on the faculty hiring front, with the latest trend being such institutions hiring from the corporate sector. Many senior managers working in the corporate sector are now switching to teaching roles in these private universities, as they offer more flexible working hours and less of deadlines and targets. The maximum switching has happened from the IT Sector, with professionals having necessary academic qualifications like M.Tech. or Ph.D. changing roles to become Assistant Professors or Professors at these universities. The offered pay is also competitive - between 80,000 to 1.5 lakh - even though it is still around 20% lower than in the corporate sector. The political aversion towards private universities too is ending in some states, with the most notable being Maharashtra. Despite pockets of resistance like Tamilnadu, Puducherry, & Kerala, private universities are here to stay. In Karnataka as on 01/06/2015, eleven private universities have started to function as per UGC status declaration in its website.

This paper focuses on how a private university can plan its MBA programme so innovatively compared to public universities based on their intention and autonomy to innovate so that a distinct course is emerged out for next generation students by considering the MBA programme of a recently started private university - Srinivas University.

II. SUCCESS OF PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES

It is predicted that Private Universities in India will overtake more elite and traditional universities in world rankings “within a generation or two”, like the incredible growth of private universities in developed countries. The traditional universities in India are lagging behind in rankings due to a lack of investment in research and the private sector provides the solution to “getting the brains back into the country”. “Two generations ago, all the best schools were provided by the public sector - now it has flipped around and it is expected that same will happen in higher education within a generation or two [2-3].

Among the private universities in India, two universities are doing extremely well in Business management education. They are Amity University, Noida and Alliance University, Bangalore. Amity University is owned by the non-profit foundation of the AKC Group of Companies, which operates petrochemical, technology and pharmaceutical firms, among others. It has provided higher education in India since 1995 (with university status since 2005) and has nine campuses in India, along with international campuses in London, Singapore, New York, California, Mauritius, Romania, Abu Dhabi, South Africa, China and Dubai. Similarly, Alliance University, Bangalore is a Private University established in Karnataka State during 2010. The university is successfully offering MBA programme with variety of specializations. The MBA programme of Alliance University is rated high compared to all public sector universities in the state.

III. MBA PROGRAM

The MBA (Master of Business Administration) degree is perhaps the world's best known and most widely recognized post graduate degree. It is a professional degree - in that it prepares or further prepares individuals for responsible positions in business - usually managerial positions. Despite its venerable age (the first MBA degrees were awarded in the early twentieth century), MBA programmes remain both popular and relevant. MBA programs are run throughout the world, as they are seen to be relevant for the preparation of people for work in management irrespective of the industry, business sector, the nature of the economy, etc. Although critics of the programmes have been numerous, large companies and increasingly small ones as well continue to see real value in the MBA as the first stage in a professional career in management. Though they often have very similar curricula and aims, MBA programmes are certainly not homogeneous. Many programmes differ in terms of aims, philosophies and teaching/delivery methods. Even more importantly, though, MBA students are a very diverse bunch. Walking through the campus of any leading business school, one will encounter people from many different countries, backgrounds and professions. Gone are the days – if they ever existed – when the mere possession of an MBA degree was enough to secure for the degree holder a rosy future at the top level of a large corporation, complete with large salary and generous perks. Many MBA students, to be sure, do graduate into such jobs. Others don't. The initials MBA no longer have the pulling power they did thirty years ago. Corporate recruiters no longer take the MBA degree itself as a guarantee of quality. They look for many other factors, including:

- the school from which the degree was granted
- the programme which the graduate is attending or has attended
- what practical experience the graduate may have gained while on the programme and, most important of all,
- the personal qualities of the graduate, including evidence of personal development while on the programme

Increasingly, companies are looking generally, at the qualities of the institution, and specifically, at the individual graduate and his or her qualities. In other words, they are not looking for the MBA degree, but for the *quality of the person who has it*.

Getting an MBA degree, therefore, is ultimately about developing students, improving their own personal qualities and improving their ability to manage. This applies whether the student is looking to change jobs or career paths, seek advancement within a firm for which they already work, or start their own business.

The MBA is a once-in-a-lifetime experience. It is, or can be, extremely expensive in terms of money and time. For most who go on such programmes, it is a life-changing experience. In order to maximize the value of the MBA, students need to look beyond the basics of classroom learning, important though these are, and consider such issues as

- gaining practical experience

- developing networks and relationships
- developing communications and interpersonal skills
- broadening personal horizons
- learning how to learn

Now more than ever, it is important to get an MBA not just for the degree itself, but for the *experience*. The degree certificate hanging on the wall at the end of the programme is no more than a sheet of paper. What is important that comes out of the MBA is what is in student *mind*. The important benefits of the MBA include not just the knowledge that one absorbs while on the programme, but the necessary learning skills that accompany this. The two are combined in a single system referred as *knowledge management*. It is argued that the MBA is a first step in a process of lifelong learning, and this is a formative learning experience. The ideas and skills gained here will affect the students personal and professional life forever after. Many candidates go into an MBA program seeking a career change. During recruitment season they find that their skills are fairly valued only by businesses in the industry that they wanted to leave behind.

Recently started concept of private universities in India provides quality education of international standards to our youth so as to utilise their knowledge in the overall development of the nation. The private universities can do lot of innovation in MBA programme structure and make it effective, attractive but affordable to common man. Private universities unlike so called top business schools can maintain the quality and credentials of MBA programme at low cost so that they can make MBA degree affordable.

IV. INNOVATIVENESS OF PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES IN MBA PROGRAM

The challenge for sustainability and return on investment of self financing institutions like Private universities usually do innovations through very hard work for improving the quality and other aspects of the higher education programme to attract both students and industries. The public universities do not face such challenge do to continuous financial support provided by the Government towards development and maintenance which results in less focus on innovations in higher education programmes. In case of MBA programme, the private universities give emphasis on following issues to differentiate and add values to their programmes :

(i) Quality : Quality education is the fundamental criterion of Private universities. By providing innovative MBA model, latest industry oriented syllabus, qualified and experienced faculty members, experimental project based learning & self involving models, industry & technology exposure, all round development opportunities, and continuous assessment system improves the confidence of students to take challenges and make best decision among alternatives.

(ii) Infrastructure : State of the art infrastructure is provided in Private University MBA programmes with executive, technology supported, multi-media enabled classrooms, digital library facility, computer labs with high speed internet and wi-fi based internet facility, Specialisation based training labs, Tutorial rooms and cafeteria facilities. The infrastructure provided in the business school supports the students for comfortable learning.

(iii) Curriculum : The comprehensive curriculum developed by Private Universities with autonomy to upgrade every year provides blending of both the theory and practice in the syllabus of core and specialised subjects. The emphasis on core subjects both on knowledge and skill based curriculum and well focussed area of specialisation develops students to be useful to the industries or to be an effective entrepreneur. The width and depth of the syllabus both in functional specializations and super specialization area improve the competency of the graduates to be successful in whatever responsibility taken in their life.

(iv) Varieties : Based on autonomy and for survival of existence, MBA programmes of Private university are becoming more innovative by providing variety of specialisations in the form of dual/multi specialisations or super specialisations. These specialisations are developed based on industry requirements and students demand. Private universities have opened up their mind came out from conventional & traditional MBA programmes unlike Public universities in India and making MBA programme as unique, industry friendly. As a result, MBA programmes in Private Universities becoming more flexible, vigorous and project oriented with many specialization opportunities. Based on experience and research ability of

students, they can opt for new subjects for specialisation with self study option like many foreign Universities in developed countries.

(v) Industry Collaborations : The curriculum and the syllabus of the programme is prepared by a committee called Board of Studies which consists eminent people selected from both industries and academics. The private Universities usually constitute Board of Studies consisting equal number of experts from industries and academics whereas in the Public Universities, in most of the cases, the Board of Studies consists of only academicians who are usually reluctant to change. In an effort of innovation and change to make MBA education more competitive, Private Universities are adding more industry experience component in the form of Project work in each semester and or enhanced period of project work three to six months during the course period. In addition, each student will be allotted to work under an industry mentor who is capable to guide and mould the student as an innovative thinker, confident leader and an effective decision maker. Emphasis on industry collaboration also helps the students to get better placement at the end of the programme.

(vi) Foreign exposure : Opportunities to visit and spend a period of time, to a foreign country business school and to take some courses & to visit some industries allow them to experience education and life in another culture. Most of the private universities develop such links with a number of other business schools around the world to add values to their programme. Moreover, such foreign country visit provides enhanced exposure, gives new ideas to become entrepreneurs, enhanced networking with foreign professors and creates further opportunity to collaborate for research, or confidence to seek further studies and job opportunities in such countries.

(vii) Placement : In the process of achieving good name and fame to the institution, Private university MBA programmes always give special importance to student placement. In order to provide an executive who has potential to succeed to the industries, business schools continuously strive to enhance leadership and decision making skills along with communication, analytical and technical skills of their students along with regular knowledge and experience enhancement model. A separate placement cell and a skill training officer appointed by the institution continuously supports the students in this regard and guides students for better placement.

(viii) Alumni Networks : Networking is one of the most important benefits which the MBA programme provides. Graduates should ideally leave the programme with both the beginnings of a network (or alternatively, valuable additions to pre-existing networks) and, perhaps more critically, with an enhanced ability to network. The reason for this is simple: the structure of most MBA programmes means that students *must* work together and perforce get to know one another. There is, therefore, an opportunity to use the MBA experience to develop networking abilities. In addition, they also get opportunity to network with huge alumni base of the institution. The advantages of a good network of business contacts are : exchanging news and information; knowledge resources; professional assistance and advice; personal support; and support for career advancement. The ability to network is being seen as a critical attribute in a manager by many companies today, and success in many jobs is often contingent on a manager's ability to make his or her networks perform. The special emphasis provided by MBA programmes in Private universities provides enhanced opportunity for students to encash the benefits of networking.

(ix) Premiere Fee Structure : Based on innovation and customization, private universities are adding higher value to their MBA programme which allows them to charge substantially higher fees. Such return on investment allows them to do further innovation and to improve the quality.

(x) Crash Course Model : Innovative MBA programmes keeps the students busy during entire two years period by doubling the subjects compared to Govt. universities. Due to increased number of subjects, electives, projects at the end of the each semester, students are deprived of annual vacation. The working days for private MBA programme will be almost double compared to traditional MBA programme of Govt. universities.

(xi) Examination System : Innovations in examination system initiated by private universities stress on continuous evaluation. The improved examination system focus on evaluating the depth of understanding rather than memorising large amount of information. Innovation in examination system forced universities

to change annual examination system to semester system, trimester system and now, each semester is further divided into two parts and examination is conducted for first half of the subjects during mid-semester and remaining half of the subjects during end-semester. This dilutes the examination fear of the students.

V. COMPARISON OF MBA PROGRAM OF PRIVATE & GOVT. UNIVERSITIES

The various features of MBA programme of Private and Govt. universities are compared in table 1.

Table 1 : Comparison of MBA Program of Private & Govt. Universities

S.No.	Features	Govt. University (MU)	Private University (SU)
1	Curriculum Aspects	Obsolete	Current
2	Additional Fees (admission approval, Eligibility, Exam Fee etc.)	High	Low
3	Student services	Low rated	High rated
4	Examination Q.P.	Less planned	Well planned
5	Transparency in Examination	Low	High
6	Publishing Result	3 months after the exams	10 days after the exams
7	Supplementary exam	Weight of one year	Within 15 days after announcing result
8	Final Result & Marks cards	Uncertainty in Result announcement and extends up to the end of August	Assured degree by 30th April for eligible students
9	Award of Degree Certificate	After 1 to 2 years	Within a month of provisional result.
10	Innovation in Syllabus	Low	High
11	Research	Low	High
12	Evaluation system	Closed & non transparent	Open & transparent
13	Quality	No bother on quality due to financial support by Government	Worried about sustainability through quality
14	Examination & Evaluation model	Credit based system	Performance based system
15	Support for placement	No worry on student placement	Priority for student placement by providing soft skill trainings
16	Industry projects & Evaluation	Not encouraged in curriculum	Encouraged in curriculum and properly evaluated through compulsory presentation & viva
17	Number of subjects /semester	five	ten
18	Experimental learning opportunity	no	yes
19	Self learning electives	Not available	Available
20	Teaching Model	Conventional classroom teaching with focus on theory	Emphasis on case studies and group discussions along with theory
21	Design of the Syllabus	Focus on Knowledge enhancement	Focus on confidence building, skill development and experience enhancement
22	Specialisations/electives	One specialization in conventional functional area	Dual or multi-specialisation opportunity in functional and super specialised areas
23	Learning model	Examination specific	Effective Decision making specific
24	Teaching Hours	Planned for 10.00 am to 4.00 pm with 5 days per week	Planned for min 10-12 hours per day with 6 days per week
25	Working days for students	More holidays & vacations. Runs as general masters programme	More working days and no vacation. Emphasis on crash course
26	Project evaluation system	Not vigorous. No viva & project presentation by the student. Project guide has no role in evaluation of the project	Emphasis on project presentation and viva with project guide as one of the evaluator
27	Industry Project Duration	One month Industry project opportunity	3 – 4 months industry project opportunity
28	Personality development	Less focus on personality development	More focus on personality development
29	Study Material support	Students have to write down important points discussed in the classrooms	Well developed, tested study materials distribution to every student with case studies, practical exercises, assignments
30	Student Development	Syllabus oriented training	Training based on overall development of the student

VI. MBA PROGRAMME – A CASE OF SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

The MBA programme structure and calendar plan is given in table 2 and 3 respectively. The various unique features are listed below :

1. Personalized Curriculum :

Students have opportunity to select specialization papers as per their wish and in selected cases they can design the syllabus of their special paper in consultation with a professor. This offer allows them to be specialised in a unique area where the systematic study is underway.

2. Dual Degree Opportunity :

Students can register for two degrees simultaneously in the same University as day programme and evening programme. For example, a student registered for MSW or MCA can simultaneously register for MBA evening programme. Students who are doing M.Tech., M.Pharm., MPT, MD, MDS, M.Sc. (Nursing) etc. Can also register for MBA (Evening) Programme provided they fulfil other admission eligibility of the programme.

3. Overseas Study Program :

The Overseas Study Program (OSP) for one week is a capstone subject with an exposure to the global dimensions of business through overseas learning components. The OSP is conducted in an international setting where students who opt for the OLP are required to travel to key international destinations in Asia, Europe or America to deepen their scholarship levels and experience. The OSP at U.K./USA for one week is offered as an optional subject in the fourth Semester of MBA course, and students are required to bear the costs of travel and visa fees as well as boarding and lodging expenses based on actual.

4. Self-directed Global Projects :

The students have option to carry out their projects in any country based on their contacts and prior experience. Students have option to do their projects in their own firms so that they can contribute the innovations in their firms during study period.

5. Student Exchange Programmes :

One week student exchange programme will be organized every year in which students will go to another nearby business school and attend a specially planned programme along with the existing students of that school. This will create networking opportunity, studying with new environment and exposure with new faculty members.

6. Semester Abroad Program & Dual Degree Programmes :

The students have option to study their second year abroad based on agreement with selected USA and European universities. The credits of the first year study of this university is honoured by foreign university for second year admission of MIB or MS programme. Similarly, the credits of MIB/MS programme is accepted by this university so that at the end of two years, such students will get dual degree, one from this university and the other from foreign university.

7. Well Planned Academic Calendar :

The entire course is well planned and organized to complete it within specified time as a crash course with all embedded and promised qualities so that they should become graduate without delay in semesters, projects and announcement of the academic results so that they should the provisional degree without any delay. This supports the students to get into the job market quickly. The sample course calendar plan of MBA programme is shown in table 3.

8. LEAD Certificate Programme to Every Student :

Soon after the induction programme, before starting the regular semester, a one week leadership development programme LEAD (Leadership Effectiveness & Development) is provided to the students to inculcate leadership qualities among them. This include motivation lectures, case studies, Success stories of executives, documentaries, group discussions, In-basket excursions, role plays, business games, sessions on emotional intelligence, flip classes etc.

9. IGNITE Certificate Programme to Every Student :

An intensive certificate programme IGNITE (Innovation & Genius in Technology Exploring) on technology innovation and possible future business opportunities prepares students to explore ideas to start new business using anticipated new technology breakthroughs like nanotechnology, bio-technology, food & drinking water technology, Sustainable energy technology and any other area of future business potential.

10. Chakrerviewha - Management Students Competition :

In order to improve the competitive spirit of the students, it is planned to conduct internal competition to test abilities of students while solving the problems in functional areas of business and in leadership challenges.

11. Four Projects during the entire course :

Students have to do compulsory projects at the end of each semester. The duration of the projects varies from one month to three months. These projects include industry analysis, empirical research, industry Internship & specialization based projects.

12. Project Guide & Industry Mentor to each student :

Along with a faculty guide, each student will be allotted to work under an experienced industry mentor who is capable to guide and mould the student as an innovative thinker, confident leader and an effective decision maker. This will support the student to re-define his career goal.

13. Personalized electives :

Students have the option to take a maximum of eight credits across courses (Elective courses) of independent study, such as Contemporary Concerns Study or Dissertation. These courses are guided by faculty and provide students an opportunity to personalize their academic work to pursue their specific areas of interest in depth.

14. Non-credit Paper on Job Searching Skills :

In the second year students are exposed to job searching skills by providing non-credit regular job searching skill development training through placement & training cell. This provide an edge in Identifying and en-cashing better opportunities in national and international placements

15. Maths Bridge Course as optional to enhance quantitative analytical skills :

To maintain all students in same level in quantitative analysing ability, the students without maths background will be provided an opportunity to take maths bridge course with various short cut methods in calculus, complex functions and using matrix method in problem solving as optional subject. This will be completed for registered students before the induction programme.

16. Opportunity to Journal Publication :

Students are encouraged and supported to present their research project papers in National /International conferences and publication in International Journals. It is desirable to publish at least one paper when a student awarded degree.

17. Dual/Multi Specializations :

Dual/Multi Specializations opportunity in general functional areas like Finance, Marketing, Human Resource Management, Entrepreneurship & Small business, Banking & Insurance, International Business and **Super specialty electives** like Business Analytics, Internet Business, Nanotech Business, Health Management, Energy Management, Public Administration, Sports Management etc. with independent study opportunity. Even though dual specializations with 12 papers are compulsory for completion of the course, students can take additional specialization based on their interest under multi specialisations option.

18. Syllabus Based Contact Classes :

Four sessions teaching classes per day of one and half hours duration on week days on regular subjects based on syllabus to enhance Knowledge & Skills.

19. Weekly Business Experience Enhancement Day :

Every Saturday is Business Experience Enhancement Day (BEED) with Team & Group activities. This includes Student Presentations, Student Union Programmes, Industry visits, Exhibitions, New Venture Competition club, Student Forum activities, Student Club activities, Online Investment Club, Games club, Speakers Club, National Service Scheme (NSS) etc. that provide distinct opportunities for learning, networking, and socializing outside the classroom.

20. E-LAB :

Entrepreneurship-Lab is a hands-on course, where students learn by doing. Students will spend a lot of time meeting and talking with their host company, potential customers, and industry/technology experts with the emphasis being on identifying attractive target market(s), defining customer value propositions, specifying

product/technology requirements and developing market entry strategies. The course sessions that students attend will focus on learning the practical tools and skills required to complete their projects.

21. Institutional Teaching/Learning Materials to every students :

Session Plan Booklet & Printed Study Materials with information as per the syllabus, case studies, readings, illustrations, assignment questions, question banks and various excursions are given to every students in all the subjects.

22. Innovation in examination system :

Innovation in examination system gives emphasis on Continuous Evaluation Choice Based Credit System with mid-semester and end-semester examinations.

23. Announcement of Results :

Examination result will be announced within a week after exam & supplementary exam before going to next semester.

Table 2 : MBA Programme structure of Srinivas university

SEMESTER I (15 + 4 = 19 WEEKS)					
S. No.	Subjects	H/w & Credit	Int. Marks	Sem. Exam Marks	Total Marks
1	Financial Accounting	4	30	70	100
2	Micro and Macro Economics for Managers	4	30	70	100
3	Business Environment	4	30	70	100
4	Management and Organizational Behaviour	4	30	70	100
5	Business Statistics/Analytics	4	30	70	100
6	Management Information System and E-Business	3	30	70	100
7	Computer Aids for Managers	3	30	70	100
8	Leadership Development	2	30	70	100
9	Business Communication	2	30	70	100
10	Mini Project 1	4	30	70	100
TOTAL		34			1000

SEMESTER II (15 + 4 = 19 WEEKS)					
S. No.	Subjects	H/w & Credit	Int. Marks	Sem. Exam Marks	Total Marks
1	Production and Supply Chain Management	3	30	70	100
2	Decision Science	4	30	70	100
3	People Management/Human Resource Management	4	30	70	100
4	Corporate Finance	4	30	70	100
5	Marketing Management	4	30	70	100
6	Business Research Methods	3	30	70	100
7	Strategic Management	3	30	70	100
8	International Business	2	30	70	100
9	Managing Innovations & Technology	2	30	70	100
10	Mini Project 2	4	30	70	100
TOTAL		34			1000

SEMESTER III (15 WEEKS)					
S. No.	Subjects	H/w & Credit	Int. Marks	Sem. Exam Marks	Total Marks
Elective : FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT					
1	Indian Financial System	4	30	70	100
2	Corporate Valuation and Restructuring	4	30	70	100
3	Financial Analysis	4	30	70	100
4	International Financial Management	4	30	70	100
Elective : MARKETING MANAGEMENT					
1	Retailing Management	4	30	70	100
2	Consumer Behaviour and Marketing Research	4	30	70	100
3	Services Marketing	4	30	70	100
4	International Marketing	4	30	70	100
Elective : HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT					
1	Industrial and Employee Relations	4	30	70	100
2	Legal Aspects in Human Resource Management	4	30	70	100
3	Strategic Human Resource Management	4	30	70	100
4	Training, Talent and Knowledge Management	4	30	70	100
Elective : BANKING AND INSURANCE					
1	Indian Banking and Financial System	4	30	70	100
2	Banking and Insurance Products	4	30	70	100
3	Principles and Practices of Banking and Insurance	4	30	70	100
4	Rural Banking & Microfinance	4	30	70	100
Elective : ENTREPRENEURSHIP					
1	Entrepreneurship and Small Business	4	30	70	100
2	Management of Start-ups and Family Business	4	30	70	100
3	Business Plan and Financing of new venture	4	30	70	100
4	Project Management	4	30	70	100
Elective : ELECTRONIC BUSINESS					
1	Electronic Business Models	4	30	70	100
2	Mobile Business Models	4	30	70	100
3	Electronic & Mobile Banking	4	30	70	100
4	Mobile Transaction Security	4	30	70	100
Elective : TECHNOLOGY MANAGEMENT					
1	Information Technology Management	4	30	70	100
2	Nanotechnology Business Opportunities	4	30	70	100
3	Customer Relationship Management (CRM)	4	30	70	100
4	Logistics and Supply Chain Management	4	30	70	100
TOTAL		32			800

SEMESTER IV (12 + 12 = 24 WEEKS)					
S. No.	Subjects	H/w & Credit	Int. Marks	Sem. Exam Marks	Total Marks
1	Opportunity Analysis & Job Search Skills	1H, Non credit	-	-	-
Elective : FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT					
5	Security Analysis and Portfolio Management	4	30	70	100
6	Risk Management and Derivatives	4	30	70	100
Elective : MARKETING MANAGEMENT					
5	Digital Marketing	4	30	70	100
6	Promotion and Distribution Management	4	30	70	100
Elective : HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT					
5	International Human Resource Management	4	30	70	100
6	Performance and Compensation Management	4	30	70	100
Elective : BANKING AND INSURANCE					
5	Treasury and Risk Management	4	30	70	100
6	Legal and Regulatory Aspects of Banking and Insurance	4	30	70	100
Elective : ENTREPRENEURSHIP					
5	Environment and Laws	4	30	70	100
6	Pricing and Marketing Strategies	4	30	70	100
Elective : ELECTRONIC BUSINESS					
5	Digital Marketing	4	30	70	100
6	Website & E-business Development (Theory + Practical)	4	30	70	100
Elective : TECHNOLOGY MANAGEMENT					
5	ERP - Retail Operations	4	30	70	100
6	ERP - Sales and Distribution (SD) or Financial Accounting (FI) – Practical Modules	4	30	70	100
7	Project based on Corporate Internship (To be carried out between Third and Fourth Semester)	8	100	200	300
8	Project Based on Empirical Research (To be carried out between Third and Fourth Semester)	8	100	200	300
TOTAL		32			1000

Table 3 : MBA Programme calendar plan of Srinivas University

Sample Programme calendar plan for the academic year 2015-16
<p>July 1st - 31st every year : Bridge Course <i>LEAD Certificate Programme</i> : 24/08/2015 to 30/08/2015 I Sem : 01/09/2015 to 24/01/2016 (20 weeks) I Sem. Classes : 01/09/2015 to 31/12/2015 (17 weeks) Exam : 21 - 31/10/2015 (Mid sem.) & 21 - 31/12/2015 (End sem.) Mini Project 1 : 1/01/2016 to 24/01/2016 (3 weeks) { Viva : 22/01/2016 - 23/01/2016 } 24/01/2016 : <i>Business Case & Business Model Analysis Workshop</i> 25/01/2016 - 31/01/2016 - Semester Break</p> <p>II Sem : 01/02/2016 to 24/ 06/ 2016 (20 weeks) II Sem. Classes : 01/02/2016 to 31/05/2016 (17 weeks) Exam : 20 - 31/03/2016 (Mid sem.) & 21 - 31/5/2016 (End sem.) Mini Project 2 : 01/06/2016 to 24/06/2016 (3 weeks) { Viva : 22/06/2016 - 23/06/2016 } 24/06/2016 : <i>Business Case Development Workshop</i> 25/06/2016 - 30/06/2016 - Semester Break</p> <p>III Sem : 01/07/2016 to 31/10/2016 (17 weeks) Exam : 22 - 31/08/2016 (Mid sem.) & 22 - 31/10/2016 (End sem.) III Sem Projects 3 & 4 : 01/11/2016 to 25/01/2017 (12 weeks) <i>Ignite Certificate Programme</i> : 01/11/2016 - 03/11/2016 Project Presentation & Viva : 23/01/2017 - 24/01/2017 25/01/2017 : <i>Career Path & Job Search Workshop</i> 26/01/2017 - 31/01/2017 - Semester Break</p> <p>IV Sem : 01/02/2017 to 25/04/2017 (12 weeks) Exam : 19 - 22/03/2017 (Mid sem.) & 25 - 28/04/2017 (End sem.) April 29-30 : Final Placement Counselling/Offers to All Successful Students April 30 /2017 : Award of Provisional Degree Certificate May 01/2017 : Research Paper presentation in Student Conference</p>

Table 4 : Quick Snap Shot of MBA Programme of Srinivas University

<p>(a) 21 Months Crash Course, (b) 32 Subjects (c) 4-5 Subjects/quarter (d) Four Projects (e) Dual /Multi specializations (f) 2 Certificate Programmes (LEAD & IGNITE) (g) 3 Workshops (h) Student Publication of Research article/Case study in Journals (i) Compulsory personality development programmes on every Saturday (j) Ultra-super specializations like Business Analytics, Internet Business, Nanotech Business Health Management, Energy Management, Public Administration, Sports Management etc. (k) Life long placement support</p>

Table 5 : Variations in MBA Programme as per customised requirement

S. No.	Course	Duration	Fee/Year (Rs.)
1	MBA (Regular) + PG Diploma in Computer Applications + PG Diploma in E-Business	2 Years	1.5 Lakhs/year
2	MBA + MIB/MS (USA) (Dual Degree) + P.G. Diploma in Computer Applications	2 (1 + 1) Years	1.5 Lakhs/year + USA Fee
3	MBA (Evening Programme)	2.5 Years Crash Course	50 K/Sem
4	MBA (Week end Programme)	2.5 Years Crash Course	50 K/Sem
5	BCA + MBA + P.G. Diploma in Software testing or P.G. Diploma in E-Business	5 Years	50 K/Sem
6	BBA + MBA + Diploma in Computer Applications	5 Years	50 K/Sem 1 Lakh/Sem
7	BBA + MBA + MIB/MS (USA)	5 Years	50 K/Sem 1 Lakh/Sem
8	B.Com + MBA + Diploma in Computer Applications	5 Years	30 K/Sem 50 K/Sem
9	B.Com + MBA + MIB/MS (USA)	5 Years	30 K/Sem 50 K/Sem + USA Fee
10	MBA + Ph.D. (Integrated)	5 Years	50 K/Sem

Table 6 : Comparative Features of MBA programme by some of the Universities :

S.No.	Parameter	SRINIVAS University	MANGAL ORE University	VTU	STANFORD University	CHICAGO BOOTH	HARVARD University
1	MBA Duration	2 Years (20 + 1 months) Crash course	2 Years (23 Months)	2 Years (23 Months)	2 Years (21 Months)	21 months	21 months
2	Core Papers	20	16	12	18	10	13
3	Elective Papers	14 + 2 (independent study) = 18	4	12	18	11	10
4	Global Experience	Yes	No	No	Yes	yes	
5	Projects/Internship	4	1	1	1	1	3
6	Special Certificate Programmes	2	-	-	1	1	-
7	Dual Degree Opportunity (SU & FIU)	Yes	No	No	Yea	Yes	-
8	Research paper Presentation in Student Conference	Yes	No	No	No	No	No
9	Cross Registration with other Schools	Yes 2 Subjects	Yes 1 Subject	-	-	-	Yes
10	Field Experience	Yes					
11	Business Case & Business Model Analysis Workshop	Yes Multiple teaching methods	No	No	-	-	-
12	Business Case Preparation Workshop	Yes	No	No	-	-	-
13	Career Path & Job Search Workshop	Yes	No	No	-	-	-
14	Section Experience (90 Students in each section)	Yes	-	-	-		
15	Entrepreneur Lab	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
16	Study Abroad (1 sem)	Available	No	No	Available	Available	Available
17	Field Work Project	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes
18	Faculty Strength In terms of Research	Highest Research Publications	-	-	High	High	High
19	Printed B school study material	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
20	Quality of Curriculum*	High	Low	Average	High	High	High

VII. CASE EXAMPLE OF COMPARISON

The MBA syllabus and the examination system of a public university and a private university are compared by taking the case example of Mangalore University and Srinivas University respectively. Table 7 shows such a comparison based on about twenty features.

Table 7 : Comparison of MBA syllabus of Srinivas University & Mangalore University

S. No	Feature	Srinivas University	Mangalore University
1	Duration	21 months	23 - 24 months
2	Number of Papers per Semester	10	5
3	Total Credit/Course	132	100
4	Total number of subjects	34	21
5	Number of Projects	04	01
6	Examination System	Modern	Classical
7	Announcement of Result	Within 10 days after exam	One to three months after exam
8	Viva & presentation for Project work exam	Both Project presentation & viva are required	No presentation & viva for project report valuation
9	Total core papers	18	16
10	Total elective papers	12	04
11	Specialization opportunity in MBA	Dual & Multi	Single Specialization
12	Number of choices in specialization	10	5
13	Admission Registration Fee	5,000	14,000
14	Examination Fee		
15	Examination System	Continuous evaluation CBCBS	CBCBS
16	Re-examination opportunity	Available before going to next semester	Available only once on a year
17	Examination Question paper model	Mix of short answer & long answer questions	Only Long answer questions
18	Quality of Curriculum	Classical style with small upgradation during revision	Radical changes as per latest industry requirement
19	Curriculum design team	Mix of industry & Academic people	Only Professors having more than 30 years experience.
20	Reference books in the syllabus	Recent editions	More books of five or more years old.

Table 8 : Comparison of total credit, duration, number of papers to be studied and fee structure of some of MBA/PGDM programmes based on information from their website.

B-School	Total Credit (for 2 years)	Programme duration (Months)	Number of Papers	Fee
IIM, Ahmedabad	514 + 350 Hours	21	30 + 25 = 55	17 lakhs
IIM, Bangalore	50 + 45 = 95	20	18 + 18 = 36	17 lakhs
TAPMI, Manipal	61 + 54 = 115	21	22 + 23 = 45	13.5 lakhs
SRINIVAS University (SU)	68 + 64 = 132	21	30 + 4 Projects	3 lakhs
Mangalore University (MU), Mangalore	50 + 50 = 100	23	20 + 1 Project	1.6 lakhs
Visvesvaraya Technological University (VTU)	48 + 52 = 100	23	25	1.6 lakhs
IIM, Lucknow	60 + 45 = 105	21	22 + 20 = 42	11 lakhs
IIM, Kozhikode	61 + 45 = 106	21	26 + 16 = 42	8 lakhs
Kirloskar Institute of Advanced Management Studies, Harihar	66 + 60 = 126	21	-	9.5 lakhs
Alliance Business School, Alliance University, Bangalore	-	24	17 + 13 = 30 + 2 Projects	13.5 lakhs
Amity Business School, Amity University, Noida	-	22	16 + 14 = 30 + 2 Projects	10 lakhs

VIII. ABCD ANALYSIS OF PUBLIC & PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES BASED ON MBA PROGRAMME

Using focus group method, the advantages benefits, constraints and disadvantages of public and private universities are analysed and are listed below under organisational, students, faculty, parental and societal issues.

1. Advantages :

(a) Advantages of Public Universities :

- (1) Organization : Financial support from the Government for development and maintenance
- (2) Students : Equal opportunity for different classes of students in the society
- (3) Faculty : Less challenge and hence preparation, more job security
- (4) Publics : Higher education opportunity for their children at low investment.
- (5) Society : Opportunity for socially deprived people based on reservation & equal opportunity.

(b) Advantages of Private Universities :

- (1) Organization : Financial sustainability through value creation & education innovation
- (2) Students : Quality education at affordable cost
- (3) Faculty : Challenges for growth & recognition for performance
- (4) Publics : Quality education to their children at affordable cost
- (5) Society : More opportunity for aspirants of higher education

2. Benefits :

(a) Benefits of Public Universities :

- (1) Organization : Catering the local education needs leads to fulfilment of organizational responsibility

- (2) Students : Higher education at low cost
- (3) Faculty : Job guarantee and other govt. facilities including pension
- (4) Publics : Subsidised higher education opportunity for their children
- (5) Society : Enhancement of higher education rate due to university contribution

(b) Benefits of Private Universities :

- (1) Organization : Name and fame for the public university for development & growth
- (2) Students : Quality education, personality development, networking, and desired placement
- (3) Faculty : Growth opportunity through competition and continuous improvement in quality
- (4) Publics : Access to quality higher education based on need
- (5) Society : More higher education opportunity for realize the dream of all aspirant which created more business, jobs and hence economic growth of the society.

3. Constraints :

(a) Constraints of Public Universities :

- (1) Organization : Financial constraints due to depends on Government funding, Constraints on innovation in curriculum
- (2) Students : Less innovated curriculum with delayed updating.
- (3) Faculty : less opportunity to continuous improvement in curriculum and industry orientation
- (4) Publics : Lower quality education to their children and hence less comparative opportunity in carrier growth
- (5) Society : Limited seats available in higher education which fails to fulfil the demand.

(b) Constraints of Private Universities :

- (1) Organization : Various Govt. regulations to speed up organizational development
- (2) Students : Comparatively high fees
- (3) Faculty : Low performers cannot sustain
- (4) Publics : High cost for quality education
- (5) Society : No substantial constraint to the society.

4. Disadvantages :

(a) Disadvantages of Public Universities :

- (1) Organization : Less opportunity for innovations due to various controls
- (2) Students : Image on quality and limited number of admissions
- (3) Faculty : Time based career growth rather than performance oriented promotions
- (4) Publics : Location and limited opportunity to their children
- (5) Society : Less contribution to economic development.

(b) Disadvantages of Private Universities :

- (1) Organization : Huge investment for establishment
- (2) Students : Higher initial investment
- (3) Faculty : No job security for poor performers
- (4) Publics : No considerable disadvantage for public by private universities
- (5) Society : No considerable disadvantage for the society by private universities

Detailed ABCD analysis of MBA programme of Private universities under various issues like organizational issues, student issues, faculty issues, parental issues & societal issues and identifying factors affecting under the four constructs - advantages benefits, constraints, & disadvantages and finding constituent critical elements are under progress and will be published shortly.

IX. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the public and private universities are compared based on their ability to provide quality and innovative post graduate business management education in terms of quality, latest innovative curriculum, specialisations, programme duration, foreign exposure, industry orientation, networking, placement service, total credits for the programme, course fee structure, and examination system. Comparison is done by considering some of public and private universities and their ability to add values to the programme in the frame of stakeholders reference. Finally, the advantages benefits, constraints and disadvantages of public

and private universities are identified and are listed under organisational, students, faculty, parental and societal issues using focus group method.

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